

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

Qualitative assessment of leakage and other spillover potentials in selected value chains

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Transnational environmental public policies regulating supply chains such as the new European Union Regulation on Deforestation-free products (EUDR) are widely expected to contribute to environmental policy goals, such as reducing global deforestation, greenhouse gas emissions, and biodiversity loss. This report provides an overview of indirect effects and mechanisms that may either hinder or further boost these goals. These indirect effects are often hard to measure, but we assess the current state-of-the-art knowledge. Combined with our interview data, we derive our expectations about likely effect directions and magnitudes. We discuss the implications also vis-à-vis the expected functioning of the EUDR.

First, we aim to clarify key concepts related to indirect effects, followed by a theoretical framework outlining their potential moderators. These generically termed “spillover effects” are indirect impacts a policy may cause across any *domain that is external to the intervention*, such as a non-targeted space, time, agent, commodity, or combinations hereof. We describe 12 potential moderators that can increase or reduce the presence and magnitude (local to global) of different spillover effects. They can be either of a boosting (i.e., positively contribute to main policy effects) or dampening nature (i.e., negatively deduce from main effects). Within dampening effects, leakage, a usually spatially dimensioned spillover effect (cf. Section 3), is the most frequently listed, typically reducing policy effects by a certain share. Yet, additional policy evasion mechanisms were identified, by which supply chain actors could even fully avoid the policy-targeted land-use changes by shifting their activities across domains, e.g., by segregating their product-sourcing patterns according to geographically variable market regulations, or by substituting regulated for non-regulated commodities.

Second, we review the literature on quantifying indirect policy effects, focusing on two main approaches: ex-ante scenario-based models (such as equilibrium models) and retrospective ex-post statistical estimations. Ex-ante models suggest high variability in leakage (ranging 7-95%) based on different scenarios, data, and modelling assumptions, while ex-post studies of existing sectorial agreements, that can be seen as precursors to supply chain regulation, provide evidence that intended effects of the policy were at least partially compromised via spatial leakage and other spillovers occurring outside of the regulated domains. While several area-based conservation approaches have been evaluated for spillovers, particularly leakage effects, specific applications to supply-chain initiatives such as the EUDR are less common, and it remains challenging to causally attribute impacts and spillovers. We also present new empirical evidence on commodity trade stickiness and spillover effects vis-à-vis the Amazon Soy Moratorium in Brazil, suggesting to what extent trade flows have encouraged less forest clearing within their established supply chains, versus seeking out new supply-chain sources under unregulated domains.

Third, we provide contextual information on five biomass supply chains mapped out in D5.1. We discuss complementary regulations and potential spillover effects for timber supply chains in three countries – Brazil, Gabon, and Cameroon – and two additional supply chains in Brazil, namely soy and wood pulp. We then summarize stakeholder expectations in these supply chains as to future spillover

effects under the EUDR. We find stakeholders, while naturally keeping their stated potential responses flexible and open, to foresee multiple strategies, among them partial shifts to less strictly regulated markets, and a likely threat displacement in Brazil to non-forest areas.

Finally, we discuss policy implications and future research avenues in the context of supply-chain governance. Leakage and policy evasion might be curbed in size but cannot be fully eliminated -- even if interventions could manage to effectively clean-up EU supply chains. Especially market segregation strategies, supplying the EU with environmentally 'clean' (but more expensive) products, while providing domestic and/or other less regulated exports markets (e.g. in Asia) with cheaper yet deforestation-'contaminated' products will likely figure prominently among the responses of value-chain actors – especially so in commodity markets where the EU global market share is low. This underscores that supply-chain interventions and trade regulations such as the EUDR will need to be combined with other policy instruments to be likely to become effectful in global strategies to conserve forests and biodiversity.

1 INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for and trade in forestry and agricultural products is an important driver of global forest degradation and deforestation (Hosonuma et al., 2012; Pendrill et al., 2022). Challenges connect demand- and supply-side regions through the supply chains of global Forest Risk Commodities (FRC), which are characterized by complex forms of mutual interdependencies across distant regions (Lenschow et al., 2016), conceptualized as tele-coupled systems. Numerous policies and governance mechanisms have been introduced to regulate legal and/or sustainable forest and ecosystem-risk commodity supply chains (Sotirov et al., 2022, 2020), as further reviewed in CLEVER D4.1.

The European Union Regulation on Deforestation-free products (EUDR) is a prominent example of such supply chain regulation. Its main goal is to minimise the EU's contribution to deforestation and forest degradation worldwide, and thereby contribute to a reduction in global deforestation, greenhouse gas emissions and global biodiversity loss (EC, 2024). It regulates the import and export of seven forest risk commodities, namely cattle, cocoa, coffee, oil palm, rubber, soya, and wood. In this report, we will use the EUDR as our primary example of supply chain regulation, but our discussion and results are generalizable to other implemented and planned policies.

Supply-chain policy interventions target production and trade processes through intermediate goals with intended spatial impact. One example is the sought-for deforestation-free 'cleaned-up' supply chains. These interventions allegedly lead to pro-conservation outcomes further on in their causal logic, after the properly controlled pathway of policy implementation (Pacheco et al., 2021).

One direct way in which policy effectiveness would expectedly be dampened is (intended or unintended) non-compliance by operators, leading to continued placement of FRCs in EU supply chains. This can for example occur by providing false information, mixing products from different origins, and taking the risk of not getting caught. Planned controls and associated sensitive fines are designed to control for intentional non-compliance in the medium run. Non-compliance is a relevant factor that could certainly dampen policy effectiveness. However, by nature it is not a spillover (or leakage) effect. We will thus discuss non-compliance and the role of monitoring and sanctioning instead in CLEVER D5.3, as a factor within the entire theory of change.

Nevertheless, actors along biomass supply chains, often even while complying with the respective supply-chain policy (e.g., EUDR, EUTR, or Amazon Soy Moratorium) that contains regulatory loopholes (e.g., some domains are subject to the rules, other are left out), are expected to respond flexibly and opportunistically to policy interventions, according to their interests to minimize incremental costs or risks. Thus, they may in so-called market segregation strategies shift production and trade from more to less stringent (or less effectively regulated) jurisdictions, domains and market segments (Lambin et al., 2018), as long as this does not trigger high opportunity cost in terms of violating social norms (e.g., high pressure from civil society). Such underlying processes often imply that policies and governance initiatives aimed at regulating global public goods, such as biodiversity conservation and global climate change mitigation,

can suffer efficiency losses in reaching their ultimate, forest-focused goals, due to opportunistic behaviour of regulatory targets - which may add to the efficiency losses suffered from regulatory loopholes and/or non-compliance (Köthke and Sotirov, 2024; Sotirov et al., 2022).

These derived effects are oftentimes generically referred to as “spillovers”. We follow Meyfroidt et al. (2020) and employ the term “spillover” for any indirect impacts a policy might have on external, non-targeted domains, such as different regions, times, agents, or commodities. In Section 3.1, we first characterize the encompassing family of spillover effects; we generically distinguish for such policy-adaptive behaviour between policy-dampening and -boosting effects assessed against the benchmark of what goals a particular policy intervention seeks to achieve. Within the adaptive behaviours that may dampen policy effectiveness, we differentiate between two specific types of spillovers, namely leakage and other evasion strategies, delimitating what they mean when interventions such as the EUDR are not directly targeting an area based conservation outcome (as the EU does not have jurisdiction in producer countries), but rather a business process towards deforestation-free supply chain that is supposed to have an indirect conservation spinoff effect.

With the EUDR scheduled to come into force for seven targeted FRCs from 30/12/2025, we pose a timely policy-relevant research question:

1. What could possibly go wrong along a Theory of Change (ToC) of the EUDR, between reaching the alleged ‘output’ of minimizing the EU’s contribution to deforestation and degradation via fully deforestation-free EU supply chains for the targeted commodities and
 - a. Reaching the ‘outcome’ of reduced deforestation and degradation globally, while
 - b. achieving the derived ‘impact’ of safeguarding the biodiversity and environmental services these forests are harbouring?

For the same purpose, we also investigate and compare other environmental policies regulating supply chains from the past, and what they meant for leakage effects, giving us some clues about what EUDR impacts and spillover effects we can reasonably expect. In this respect, we also report new empirical results on trader stickiness, a measure inversely correlated to leakage, for the Amazon Soy Moratorium in Brazil -- a similar supply chain-focused (though spatially more restricted) intervention.

We then review the broader literature to identify generic leakage and spillover mechanisms globally at play, and factors that expectedly either came to boost or dampen these: policy design and implementation, product types and values, degrees of labour and capital mobility, technological flexibility in production (also known as factor substitution elasticity), demand elasticity, etc.

Next, we draw on our stakeholder interviews from three supplier countries (Brazil – n=70, Cameroon – n=40, and Gabon – n=33), and the EU as an importer region (n=57), using a qualitative approach. The goal is to understand the knowledge, motivation, decision-making and coalitions that underly the possible leakage-causing behaviour despite compliance to the EUDR in five focal supply chains (from D5.1):

- Brazil-EU soy
- Brazil EU timber
- Brazil-EU wood pulp
- Cameroon-EU timber
- Gabon-EU timber

These supply chains are significant for key supply- and demand-side regions, particularly in the Amazon and Congo Basin rainforests, which in turn are crucial harbours for global biodiversity – yet significantly impacted by deforestation and forest degradation for soy production and selective logging, with the EU playing a non-trivial role in driving demand for forest-risk commodities, as shown in D5.1.

In this report, we aim to help framing the quantitative modelling of spillover effects to be implemented in Module C (WP6-7), where CLEVER will develop extensions of the GLOBIOM modelling platform. The information here provided can hopefully improve the understanding of the impacts of governance intervention at global and regional scales.

2 OBJECTIVES

Informed by the overarching research question in Section 1, this report's specific objectives are, aligned with a specific interest in the EUDR but with generalizable policy lessons relevant also to other supply chain regulations, to:

- I. identify and frame variable spillover effects with general relevance for supply chain policies,
- II. describe the expected pathways and mediators of these effects, and
- III. quantify and/or qualitatively characterize spillover effects emerging within selected policies and supply chains through literature review and stakeholder interviews.

Based on this, we aim to derive broad-based lessons regarding the likely effectiveness of supply-chain policies under different contextual scenarios – including by foreshadowing to-be-expected EUDR impact and spillover effects – and assess possible leverage points along international supply chains for forest and biodiversity conservation.

3 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Pro-environmental supply-chain interventions range from the voluntary certification of primary commodity production (e.g., of sustainable and fair coffee trade or forest management) to industry-wide pro-environmental sectoral agreements (e.g., for zero-deforestation production) and, finally, the full non-voluntary exclusion of goods associated with environmentally damaging production practices from targeted supply chains. Along this sequence from voluntary incentive-rewarded commitments to disincentive-penalized, forced demands for supply chain compliance, the EUDR lies clearly at the latter end: it represents a quantitative trade restriction acting primarily as a targeted disincentive tool for commodity importers into the EU. Even under a scenario where supply-chain actors were to receive some financial and technical support for securing compliance, under any set of normal economic-theory assumptions the burden to comply with the EUDR would trigger incremental costs and reduced profit margins, compared to the counterfactual business-as-usual situation of “no EUDR”.

How would we thus, hypothetically speaking, imagine an ideal situation of cleaned-up, i.e., legal and deforestation free, supply chains directly resulting in environmental gains for forests, biodiversity and ecosystem services, without being jeopardised by any secondary or indirect effects on policy effectiveness? Already the announcement of the EUDR's future implementation, currently set at the end of 2025, should here have come to curb the demand for lands in producer countries that were cleared after the 2020 cut-off date, and will thus become EU market-incompliant. This should continue to decrease the demand for lands deforested after the cut-off once implementation starts, ideally leading even to some abandonment of recently cleared lands, allowing over time for their (active or passive) reconversion to forestlands and other native vegetation.

In practice, however, actors within biomass supply chains tend to respond flexibly and adaptively to policy interventions depending on context and interaction with other actors, which may include shifting production and sales from jurisdictions and market segments with higher to lower levels of regulatory standards or enforcement (Lambin et al. 2018). Producers and intermediaries may respond to policies by applying policy-evasive strategies minimizing the added costs and/or risks, thus resulting in indirect policy effects, as we describe in the following section. Although conditions can thus be identified under which supply-chain interventions are most likely to succeed in generating ‘clean’ deforestation-free supply chains, this will not automatically imply reduced deforestation: large de-facto discrepancies (i.e., the targeted operators are not the ones making proper land-use decisions) prevail in this quintessential transition within the theory of change for environmental supply-chain interventions (Garrett et al. 2021). This also means that supply-chain policies and governance initiatives aimed at regulating global public goods, such as biodiversity conservation and global climate change mitigation, tend to suffer cost-effectiveness losses.

These indirect effects, occurring outside of the policy-targeted domain of space, time, commodities, or agents, are also referred to as spillover effects. Especially when spatial displacement is involved, the term “leakage” has been involved, though some authors use “slippage” to refer to the same phenomenon (Pfaff &

Robalino 2017, Wu 2000). In the following subsection, we aim to streamline an often somewhat variable wording in the literature on policy impacts into a hopefully more consistent terminology, distinguishing different types of indirect policy effects (i.e., spillovers). We then outline the main mechanisms behind different spillovers and assess their drivers.

3.1 SPILLOVER EFFECTS

Following Meyfroidt et al. (2020), we use the umbrella term “spillovers” to generically describe any indirect impacts a policy may cause across any external, non-targeted domain – such as space, time, agents, or commodities. For example, the target domain of the EUDR is forests, yet spillovers can occur into non-forest lands, such as from the (regulated) Amazon forests into the (non-regulated) neighbouring Cerrado biome. Similarly, the EUDR targets seven FRCs, yet deforestation pressures could instead partially spill over into other FRCs (e.g., sugarcane, manioc, maize etc.). Likewise, the EUDR targets EU imports, but affected producers on newly deforested lands could instead sell to lower-regulated markets (e.g., Asia, domestic markets), if there is demand. An omnipresent policy that was to hypothetically encompass all possible multidimensional domains simultaneously would also leave no more spillovers to operate but is unlikely to be implementable in practice.

By their nature, spillover effects can either be positive (boosting the main policy impact) or negative (dampening it); they can be intended or unintended, and expected or unexpected. Various forms of spillovers have been distinguished in the literature, including leakage, indirect land-use change, and rebound effects (Meyfroidt et al., 2018). Figure 1 provides a schematic overview of different spillovers discussed in the following.

Figure 1. Conceptualisation of spillovers

For the EUDR, ‘dampening’ is the process by which a successful supply-chain cleaning-up policy would fail to reduce deforestation in target areas, and/or cause new deforestation elsewhere, thus overall reducing global policy effectiveness. Hereunder, ‘evasion’ is the process by which actors would segregate supply chains and markets so that land uses and deforestation in and outside the targeted domain remain unaffected by the policy, thus leaving no observable effect on deforestation. Conversely, boosting is the process by which a policy was to cause less deforestation elsewhere, thus increasing policy effectiveness beyond the targeted domain.

3.1.1 Dampening effects

3.1.1.1 Leakage

The leakage term has traditionally been used to refer to “changes in emissions and removals of greenhouse gases (GHG) outside the accounting system that result from activities that cause changes within the boundary of the accounting system” (Watson et al., 2000). For instance, classical carbon leakage occurs when efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions or changes in environmental policies in one domain (inside effects) lead to the unintended consequence of shifting these emissions to areas not subject to the same regulations (outside effects). This concept gained attention with the Kyoto Protocol (Antimiani et al., 2013; Felder and Rutherford, 1993; Paltsev, 2001), which required countries to reduce their emissions and prompted significant research on leakage effects. REDD+ programmes, as voluntary initiatives aiming at reducing forest loss-related emissions, spurred further research on leakage (Atmadja and Verchot 2012).

According to Meyfroidt et al. (2020), for **leakage *sensu stricto*** three necessary conditions define the term: it must 1) be causally **linked to a policy** intervention, 2) affect the **same outcome** variable as targeted by the policy intervention (e.g., forest cover), and 3) it must have the **opposite sign** of the direct policy impact (i.e., dampen the intended effect of a policy). It is thereby defined via its outcome, so leakage and its effect are identical. Interventions restricting opportunities to exploit natural resources can, for instance, partially displace those activities and their environmental effects to other areas. The most considered negative spillover effect is threat-displacing leakage (Filewod & McCarney, 2023).

However, there are multiple underlying mechanisms, and other types of spillovers that are not leakage. In the context of area-based conservation policies, different pathways of indirect land-use change effects have been described. Indirect land-use change refers to changes in land-use that are caused, but not targeted by an environmental policy. These pathways include economic forces (e.g., agents moving activities, or reacting to changing market prices), but also human learning, altered motivations, institutional interactions, and ecological-physical links (Pfaff and Robalino, 2017). The scope can be local (e.g., protected-area buffer zones), regional/national (e.g., emigration of settlers), or transnational (e.g., raising global commodity prices). For a comprehensive review of environmental spillover effects, see Lima et al. (2019). Some, but not all indirect land-use spillovers from area-based policies do also apply to supply chain regulations. In the following, we review the main mechanisms through which such spillovers can occur.

Activity displacement (also: activity leakage), is typically seen when the spatial coverage of the policy intervention (e.g., a carbon project) is smaller than that of the goal's objective function (e.g., global climate change mitigation). It thus occurs when conservation efforts come to partially shift environmental pressures to external, non-intervention areas. This can happen when resources (e.g., capital, labour) freed by conservation measures are redirected to other parts of a farm, when restrictions lead to labour-force migration and increase environmental pressures in new locations, or when corporations reallocate production factors to regions subject to a lesser extent of conservation policies.

In the context of global supply-chain regulations such as the EUDR, the spatial biome coverage is comprehensive, in the sense that it applies to all forests worldwide according to the FAO definition. However, this FAO definition does not necessarily align with national definitions and remote sensing-based land cover products, nor does it guarantee the highest level of biodiversity and carbon is preserved. Activity leakage can occur moving pressures to other wooded or non-wooded land not covered by the EUDR, for example in South America displacing deforestation threats from the Amazon forest to the *Cerrado* savannah biome (Villoria et al., 2022), or in Indonesia to carbon-rich wetlands or grasslands (Fleiss et al., 2022). Note, that such a shift does not always dampen the immediate goal of the EUDR, namely, to reduce its contribution to deforestation, because FRCs supply remains restricted. It would, however, compromise the derived overall goal of reduced global deforestation.

Such reallocations of activities can be mediated through markets, as changes in input and output prices can create broader incentives to change production practices. If the EUDR limits commodity exports of a country to the EU market and the demand gap was not met by other consumers, domestic output prices would drop, and producers might switch production to other commodities. If these commodities have a larger ecologic footprint in terms of deforestation, carbon and biodiversity, they may ultimately counteract the policy goal. Similarly, an EUDR-induced drop in demand may lead to a short-term oversupply of related production inputs, such as machinery or labour, which are then used elsewhere. This scenario could undermine both the primary and secondary goal of the EUDR, as deforestation leaked to non-regulated commodities can still be imported to the EU.

3.1.1.2 Evasion

Some market actors' reactions may come to fully **neutralize land-use effects**, so that policy effectiveness vis-a-vis forest outcomes fully evaporates. Product-, supplier- and market **segregation**¹ are such strategies of evading the policy, having no observable impact on the outcome of interest. For example, traders may reallocate timber from high-risk sources to domestic (Brazil, Cameroon, Gabon) or international buyers with lower regulatory standards (e.g., China, Vietnam) in a way that the same volumes are still produced at the same locations, but their trade destinations switch. This implies a continued demand for FRCs by these less stringent markets. On a conceptual level, evasion, i.e., the switching between producers, markets, commodities, is supposed to be more likely if there are more options and benefits for such a switch. On the other hand, the switch is less likely to occur when there are significant costs related to it.

For the EUDR, four additional evasion channels (i.e., indirect dampening effects different from "leakage", cf. above) can be distinguished: evasion to less regulated countries, to other markets, to other commodities, and to other exporting countries. Avoiding costs related to due diligence and providing information about geolocation of production sites imposed by the EUDR may lead producers, exporters and importers of forest risk commodities (FRC) to switch to other importing countries, markets, commodities, lands, and exporting countries. In general, producers and countries with lower compliance and traceability costs, and lower ex ante deforestation risks, have a comparative advantage for the EU market. Other producers and countries may therefore focus on domestic and other international markets with fewer restrictions. Producing and importing commodity derivatives that do not fall within the regulation provide another way to evade a supply chain policy, for example when plastic elements are added to a piece of furniture so that it is no longer legally considered a timber product.

¹ A segregated model of sourcing is used by companies separating products purchased from a certified farm from non-certified products throughout the whole supply chain

3.1.2 Boosting effects

Indirect effects on the same or different outcomes as the one targeted by the policy that have the same direction as the intended policy effect are **positive spillovers** or boosting effects (Meyfroidt et al. 2020).

Information, capacity building and investments in technical infrastructure could result in boosting effects. Actors learning about the costs and benefits of complying with the regulation may decide to voluntarily follow the standard, even if they are not directly affected by it – e.g. to anticipate expected future demands on their business practices by being ‘ahead of the curve’. The induced availability of training materials and novel products and services supporting EUDR implementation make it cheaper also for these non-targeted actors to implement standards voluntarily. Similarly, establishing effective monitoring and traceability infrastructure reduces compliance costs for actors not affected by the EUDR. They may be motivated to voluntarily adopt the standard for reasons of comparative advantage, marketing, stakeholder interests or to strategically prepare for future coverage by the EUDR. The procedural knowledge and infrastructure may also support companies in their due diligence requirements imposed by other regulations, such as the EU directive on corporate sustainability due diligence (Directive 2024/1760).

The **Brussels effect** (Bradford, 2020) poses that the EU as an attractive market and normative power can induce policy changes in other countries and trade blocs (ASEAN, MERCOSUR) resulting in the integration of EU's stricter environmental and trade regulations in these third countries. It can also favour companies' adoption of the most rigorous EU standard, which is then also applied for markets outside of the EU, if it does not incur high additional costs. Similar trends have been observed with data protection policy, consumer health regulation, hazardous substances and animal welfare regulation (Bradford, 2020). The explanation is that stricter and unified standards across the EU and third countries may benefit globally operating companies by simplifying production and exports and avoiding costs to comply with many different regulatory standards (“de facto Brussels effect”). After adapting to EU standards, companies may lobby their governments for higher regulations to offset compliance costs and gain a competitive edge. When third countries' governments adapt their rules to reflect the more stringent EU rules, either due to economic actors' lobbying or international policy diffusion (de jure Brussels effect), this results in a “race to the top” of regulatory standards across importing jurisdictions (Bradford, 2020; Vogel, 1995). The voluntary adherence to stricter regulation can be a risk mitigation strategy to reduce potential legal liabilities and reputational damage in an economically and politically competitive environment. Such spillovers on corporate and government level imply changes in private and public procurement strategies. To the extent that companies apply their EUDR-compliant procurement strategies in other regions, this shifts the overall demand for FRCs globally. Thus, the commitment of large, multinational actors in FRC supply chains to implement the regulation beyond the mandated EU market acts in favour of the overall goal of the policy.

Combination and goal dependence

The three above-mentioned spillover types are not mutually exclusive and can apply partially or together to different policy goals. For example, traders evading

regulation by resourcing commodities from non-covered areas may stimulate investments in fixed assets in those regions, thereby increasing the profitability of production in that region. This can induce increased supply and land clearing for domestic or other less stringent importing markets, potentially translating into leakage *senso strictu*. While the pure evasion would affect neither the primary goal of deforestation free supply chains, nor the secondary goal of reduced overall deforestation, the leakage effect would affect the secondary goal.

Other spillover effects

In this report, we focus on indirect effects on the same outcome of the policy goal, so, in the case of the EUDR, reducing deforestation. It is important to remember that there can also be spillover effects on other variables not defined in the policy goals, but nevertheless relevant. For example, commodity- and market segregation may require new transport routes and storage infrastructure, potentially increasing GHG emissions, which conflicts with climate change mitigation goals. Similarly, there may be impacts on labour markets affecting local incomes and poverty.

3.2 MODERATORS THAT DETERMINE SPILLOVERS MAGNITUDE

This section introduces factors that can increase or reduce the presence and magnitude of different spillover effects. Since spillovers can affect the policy effectiveness, these drivers are also moderators of the overall policy impact. Moderators refer to variables that influence the direction of the relationship between an intervention aiming to reduce deforestation and its impact. Would the clean supply chain translate in more protection of forests without deforestation regulation? We organize these factors along spatial scales, from local to global.

1. **Producer characteristics:** Existing high levels of supply-chain traceability makes leakage less likely (e.g., for cocoa; O'Brien et al. 2022). Similarly, low implementation costs for traceability, (i.e., low supply chain monitoring, reporting and verification costs) reduce the leakage risk that traders segregate and reallocate compliant and non-compliant producers and commodities. However, on the local and regional level, small farms face relatively higher monitoring, reporting and verification costs compared to large farms. In addition to limited resources, they often have less secure land tenure. Therefore, if cost-efficient traceability is present only for a subset of producers, e.g., large-scale farms and some cooperatives, it may induce evasion (segregation). This suggests a move towards plantations, larger cooperatives, and larger farmers.
2. **Land economy:** Wunder (2008) listed several factors that influence the likelihood and extent of spillover effects in the context of REDD+. Competitive and integrated land markets across regions also increase the probability of leakage. Additionally, leakage is more likely if there are available, affordable, and suitable lands outside the regulated area, as opposed to remote, well-protected, or expensive alternatives that are less suitable for conversion.

3. **Commodity profitability:** Leakage is more likely to spread widely if the market for the affected output has high price elasticity, meaning that a policy-induced reduction in supply does not significantly decrease demand. High-value activities like oil palm, soybeans, and logging are more likely to relocate despite increased transport costs, compared to lower-value activities. The relative profitability of commodities can moderate leakage by influencing where and how they are produced. For example, high market prices for commodities like soy may incentivize producers to clear new land, leading to higher leakage, while low prices might reduce this effect. The size of the market might imply more and less established infrastructures, as roads or ports, which can determine the accessibility to alternative areas for production. We will look at this moderator for the three countries, through the stakeholder interviews analysis.

4. **Fixed assets:** That is, the presence of required large scale infrastructure such as railways, ports, mills, factories, storages make leakage more likely, because users have a high opportunity cost of not using them. This lock-in effect of fixed assets may be stronger for low value commodities, since the incremental cost of new infrastructure is relatively higher. In other words, shifting sourcing regions is more likely to occur when there is a lack of fixed assets owned by companies in existing sourcing regions, and lower supply chain complexity and higher levels of traceability in other regions. However, this only holds if these fixed assets do not support and can also not be cheaply adapted to support product segregation, as this would make evasion more likely.

5. **Technological flexibility and factor mobility:** in production systems with fixed production factor coefficients, spillovers are more likely to occur, because producers cannot adapt by changing their technology. This implies suboptimal factor allocation and high opportunity costs of switching production to other domains (region, commodity). If, to the contrary, factor substitution elasticities are high and allow for flexibly adapting to land use regulation via technological change, spillovers are less likely. A precondition for making use of such technological flexibility is factor availability and mobility. For example, a farmer with two thirds of land compliant with regulation, but one third non-compliant, could decide to intensify production on the compliant area, if this is technologically feasible. Technologically feasible means that the production system allows for intensification of land use by changing other inputs, such as labour or capital. If, no suitable technology for intensification is available, the farmer has one third of land unproductive, implying a high opportunity cost and incentive to use it in some other way, e.g. cultivating a crop not covered by the regulation.

6. **Trader stickiness** refers to the persistence of traders maintaining pre-established trading links over time (Reis et al., 2020). It reflects the strength of trader-producer relations. We include stickiness here as a proxy moderators that combines and is influenced by several of the other mentioned factors (factor mobility, fixed assets), because it may be easier to observe than its underlying drivers. Stickiness can in principle have

ambiguous effects. On the one hand, it may increase the risk of deforestation. Leijten et al. (2022) used Brazilian soy export data to show that stickiness influenced business behaviours and patterns related to deforestation. This stickier sourcing pattern is also associated with higher levels of soy deforestation exposure and territorial deforestation. This means that sticky traders tend to increase deforestation due to maintenance of products demand from specific regions, encouraging production expansion and creating dependency. On the other hand, companies with a stickier sourcing pattern were more likely to adopt zero-deforestation commitments. Box 1 provides novel evidence from a voluntary due diligence agreement indicating that traders' supply-side stickiness can reduce deforestation leakage, as being the empirically dominating effect.

7. **Non-divisibility** of standards and production lines, swaying the producer/operator towards standardisation rather than customisation of products/services. This condition creates incentives for non-EU producers to apply EU standards irrespective of the ultimate market because of economic, technical or legal non-divisibility of standards, e.g., when it is not possible for a company to adjust its practices or product to different markets. On the other hand, the ease to make derived/processed products not covered by the EUDR further increases the likelihood of commodity-evasion.
8. Availability of reliable **compliance tools**: creating, maintaining and distributing traceability tools for actors along the supply chains facilitates their adoption and relative costs of compliance. Digitalization, in particular open source and transparency enhancing monitoring and verification tools like distributed ledgers can contribute to this.
9. **Risk and transaction costs**: On a global level, the EU may shift commodity sourcing towards countries from high-risk regions to low-risk regions, but only if this risk is associated with the costs of monitoring it. Similarly, this also applies to traders: those well-positioned to comply with the EUDR would supply the EU market, using fewer suppliers with sourcing from low-risk regions. As an outcome, this could effectively strengthen low-risk suppliers, such as USA. Quote: "It is expected that traders will also engage in other strategies to facilitate compliance, including adapting their supply base to source from low-risk suppliers. This could, in turn, lead to some producers, particularly smallholders, being excluded from the EU market" (O'Brien et al., 2022, p. 2).
10. **Regulatory capacity**: whether or not the Brussels effect will emerge, depends, among other factors such as market shares, target elasticity, and non-divisibility of production, on the ability to promulgate and enforce regulations. The regulatory capacity rests on the EU's preference for strict standards, which relates to regulatory and consumer ideologies in favour of precautionary regulatory intervention. On the contrary, the "Delaware effect" as a form of regulatory "race to the bottom" leads regulators to choose to lower their regulatory standards to attract businesses looking for the least stringent standard that reduces costs (Vogel 1995). If the EU's regulations are too stringent, the costs of

compliance may exceed the benefits, driving producers, exporters, and importers of forest-risk commodities to shift their operations to countries, markets, or commodities with less stringent regulations, resulting in regulatory competition-induced market spillover.

11. **Regulatory discrepancies or policy incoherence** between countries and regions (EU vs. Brazil) can increase the risk of leakage and evasion. For example, what is considered a forest, and what thresholds are applied to determine legal vs. illegal deforestation can differ across national laws. As discussed in the D4.3, the EUDR's FAO-based forest definition differ from national forest codes, in countries like Brazil, Cameroon and Gabon. This difference results in forested areas legally allowed to have a certain percentage deforested for other land use under the Forest Code. For example, the Brazilian Forest code requires protection of 80% of forested areas in the Amazon Legal area and 35% of the *Cerrado* area, which allows for 20% legal deforestation in the Amazon area or 65% in the *Cerrado* across a property. In Cameroon deforestation is permitted in some forest domains. At the same time, the EUDR forbids any EU imports of the seven forest risk commodities if they were produced on (primary) forest lands that were deforested (after 2020), regardless of whether this was legal according to the national laws (e.g., Brazil, Cameroon). Opportunistic traders can therefore redirect existing supply chains to meet requirements of domestic and external demand in consumer regions with less stringent or overall missing rules compared to the EU (e.g., China, Australia), or with matching rules (USA FOREST Act, UK Environmental Bill) recognizing the legal order of the producer countries.

12. High **market share** of implementing importers reduces risk of leakage, e.g., EU is a big market and importer of cocoa (e.g., from Western Africa) but a relatively small one for soy (e.g., from Brazil) compared to China. A high market share implies limited possibilities for producers to relocate where regulation is less stringent. Furthermore, a high market share has price-determining effect that is key to creating future expectations about FRC profitability and associated land clearing. If companies, especially multinational corporations, adopt EUDR-conforming procurement policies beyond the EU, this would increase the market share for compliant FRCs, thereby reducing the risk of spillovers. The same applies if, via the de-jure Brussels effect, i.e. additional non-EU markets adopting similar regulations.

BOX 1: TRADER STICKINESS IN BRAZIL – NEW EMPIRICAL ESTIMATES

The CLEVER project contributes to the empirical evidence on leakage mechanisms. We here summarize an unpublished original study (Oliveira et al., forthcoming) that directly addresses one of the research gaps identified in Section 4, namely the role of trader stickiness, a proxy that integrates several spillover moderators (see section 3.2).

One of the determinants of spillovers is the extent to which process by which traders reallocate or not their sourcing locations and export destinations. The extent to which traders maintain established business relationships over time and space, rather than switching to alternative relationships, has been termed stickiness (Reis et al., 2020). Traders that maintain upstream activities with producers within their global supply chains are characterized by higher levels of supply-side stickiness, while traders that maintain their downstream business links are characterized by higher levels of demand-side stickiness. Traders can be influenced by both supply-side and demand-side stickiness at the same time. Sticky traders are more likely to implement activities along their supply chain to comply with a new regulation, rather than circumventing the associated compliance requirements by switching sources and destinations. Reis et al. (2023) show that factors positively associated with the supply-side stickiness of traders include the presence of fixed assets, such as processing infrastructure, and a strong export orientation. On the other hand, volatile producer prices and insecure land tenure are negatively associated with supply-side stickiness.

In their working paper, Oliveira et al. (forthcoming) quantify how environmental policies affect supply-side stickiness, hypothesizing that supply restrictions temporarily reduce stickiness to avoid compliance costs. They study the impact of the Amazon Soy Moratorium on Brazilian soy exports to understand whether changes in traders' stickiness led to policy evasion. The soy moratorium is a voluntary agreement initiated by the private sector and supported by the Brazilian governments and NGOs, under which traders do not purchase soy from land that was deforested after 2008. Traders are expected to remain sticky if the cost of implementing a new trade link is higher than the increase in production costs associated with compliance. Cost-minimizing traders also do not incur compliance costs in addition to switching costs, so if they switch, they are also less likely to comply, leading to higher deforestation risk.

They operationalize stickiness as a normalized index ranging from zero to one, where one indicates temporal stability of trade volumes from the same sourcing regions to a trader, and zero indicates complete abandonment of previous trade relationships. They apply difference-in-differences and triple differences econometric models using data from the TRASE database². The results indicate a significant reduction in soy trader stickiness of about 11-13% after the onset of the soy moratorium. This implies that traders did indeed choose to incur the costs of establishing new trading relationships to avoid the regulation. They did so by switching to suppliers from regions outside the Amazon, such as southern Brazil, that were not covered by the regulation.

² <https://trase.earth/>

Moreover, although the Soy Moratorium reduced deforestation risk overall, the subset of traders who switched to new sources had an increased risk of deforestation (outside the Amazon). This suggests leakage, in that the policy caused an increase in deforestation risk outside the area covered by the policy. This is consistent with other studies that have found a spatial shift of production from the Amazon to other regions (Villoria et al., 2022).

In conclusion, mobile traders are likely to change their sourcing strategies to avoid compliance costs, and this may also be the case for interventions targeting global supply chains such as the EUDR. In addition to spatially switching sourcing regions from high to low deforestation risk actors along the supply chain may either switch to complementary commodities not covered by the regulation or reallocate their exports to destinations outside the European Union. Sticky traders, on the other hand, may act as supportive agents for the EUDR and create leverage points to enable more effective implementation of this type of environmental policies regulating supply chains.

4 MODELING LEAKAGE: LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviews the literature that models and quantifies leakage and other spillovers. The literature can be broadly divided into two types of studies: 1) ex-ante or scenario-based modelling approaches that rely on computational equilibrium models to assess potential impacts of planned policies, and 2) ex-post statistical estimations that exploit variation in a policy or trade patterns in relation to land use to evaluate a policy's impact after its implementation. Both approaches have been applied to various environmental policies in recent decades. In the following, the two basic approaches are presented along with empirical applications from other environmental policies, with a particular focus on forest and land use related policies. A full overview with the main findings of all reviewed empirical studies on spillovers is shown in Table 1.

Ex-ante leakage modelling

Equilibrium modelling is a common (ex-ante) approach that establishes an economic equilibrium for an entire economy and individual market sectors. These models can be combined with biophysical models, for example, to compare land use and indirect land use changes for a scenario with an environmental policy compared to a scenario without the policy. This enables causal attribution of spillover effects to policies.

Atmadja and Verchot (2012) provide a review of some of the earlier research on spillover effects. Most of the studies analysed relate to carbon-leakage effects arising from its mandatory carbon accounting or biofuel policies. Most of the papers examined use equilibrium modelling as a methodology to quantify leakage. The estimates range from 7% to 40% displaced carbon emissions. These variations are due to differences in the policy scenario tested and the way emission-causing activities and industries were defined. *Henders and Ostwald (2012)* reviewed tools to quantify carbon leakage from land use-related environmental policies, particularly the REDD+ program. While they show that

different approaches for local to national level leakage quantification are available and used by certification bodies, they point out the gap in global leakage quantification.

Henders and Ostwald (2014) then specifically focused on methods for quantifying international, in particular trade-related indirect land use effects. According to them, equilibrium modelling is a powerful, top-down tool to assess potential leakage of policies when coupled with regional land use models but may suffer from limited specificity with respect to regions, products and sectors. Two major types of equilibrium models can be used for leakage estimation (Henders and Ostwald, 2014). First, computable general equilibrium (CGE) models represent the entire global economy with aggregated products and regions and can incorporate price changes in related sectors and products. Second, Partial Equilibrium models do not include such price changes but can disaggregate products and regions to provide more detail to an analysis. Both types come with specific sets of assumptions and data requirements. With this in mind, we now turn to an overview and summary of equilibrium modelling studies related to forest conservation and land use policies.

The Agricultural Policy Regional Impact Analysis (CAPRI) model has been used to quantify the impact of a theoretical implementation of greenhouse gas reduction targets on agriculture. The results show a leakage effect of up to 91 %, which is due to a shift in trade balances and displacement of the agricultural processing industry to countries outside the EU (Fellmann et al., 2018).

Gan and McCarl (2007) provide a global CGE-application of how forest conservation policies in one country may induce leakage to other countries depending on price elasticities. They find that in tele-coupled trade systems, when few countries collaborate, leakage can compromise up to 95% of the environmental gain. Similarly, Nepal et al. (2013) found that paying forest owners in the United States for sequestering carbon rather than harvesting trees would incur 71-85% carbon leakage within the country. The authors considered a hypothetical large-scale voluntary timber set aside payments scheme and modelled different carbon price scenarios using the U.S. Forest Products Module (USFPM) and Global Forest Products Model (GFPM).

Busch et al. (2022) describe the effects of hypothetical demand restrictions for deforested palm oil in Europe on deforestation in Indonesia, simulated backwards in time: what would have happened to trade flows and land use, had these measures been applied over the last 15 years? The authors modelled the effects by integrating the global trade model GTAP-BIO and the OSIRIS model for land use change in Indonesia. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the only one that describes and models market leakage/ spillover effects in relation to agreements on deforestation-free supply chains. Results suggest that European demand-side restrictions on high-deforestation palm oil from 2000 to 2015 would have led to a price premium for low-deforestation palm oil (8.9%) but would have had only minimal effects on deforestation (-1.60%) and emissions from deforestation (-1.91%) in Indonesia. Regarding evasion, about half (52%) of the high-deforestation palm oil that would otherwise have been exported to Europe would shift to other export regions or the domestic market.

In sum, there is considerable variation in estimated leakage, but all studies indicate that it is of relevant magnitude. For a meta-analysis of leakage effects in the forest sector estimated with general and partial equilibrium models, see Pan et al. (2020). Based on 19 studies, they estimate the average carbon leakage in the forest sector to be 40%.

Ex-post leakage estimation

Ex-post studies take a retrospective view on implemented policies and employ statistical methods such as regression analysis to identify how the implementation of a policy was related to outcomes of interest. Empirical approaches exploit exogenous variation in policy implementation patterns to disentangle their impact from other factors that occurred at the same time or place and would confound the identification.

Several empirical studies have linked spatially explicit environmental leakage effects of conservation policies within regions and countries, see Pfaff and Robalino (2017) for a review. Yet, the studied conservation programs were spatially delineated, e.g., as protected areas or specific pieces of land enrolled in payment schemes. Many of the tools and methods employed by these studies are thus not suited to study spillovers of international trade and supply chain policies that are not spatially bounded in the same way.

Parra Paitan and Verburg (2019) revisited and extended the review by Henders and Ostwald (2014), comparing empirical as well as modelling approaches with respect to their capacity to spatially allocate indirect land use changes. They review life-cycle assessment, environmental footprints analyses, agent-based models, system-dynamics models, equilibrium models along with input-output models and land-use models. While these approaches by themselves lack the ability to assess spatial spillover effects of trade, their combination can to some extent achieve this. One example, also highlighted by Hender and Ostwald (2014), is the extended material flow analysis (MFA). In land-use studies using this method, physical trade flows from input-output models are usually translated into consistent, analysable units, such as the area required for agricultural production, timber equivalents or forest-carbon stocks.

Hong et al. (2022) used a combination of global multi-regional input-output, land-use and emission models to quantify land-use emissions embodied in trade. They isolate the emissions from land-use change, vis-à-vis other production related emissions. They find that 27% of all land-use emissions were related to agricultural products consumed non-domestically. They also identified the largest trade-based transfers of land-use emissions, namely Brazil, Argentina, and Indonesia as the top net emission exporters, and China, the US, Japan, and Germany, as the largest net importers in 2017. While such overall quantifications are very informative, this approach does not causally attribute the land use changes to a specific policy.

In contrast, Meyfroidt and Lambin (2009) used this method to analyse leakage effects in the Vietnamese timber market. Atmadja and Verchot (2012) describe the material flow analysis and the study by Meyfroidt and Lambin (2009) as an important step, as this methodology is able to assign the changes in the market to a driver, in contrast to the modelling otherwise used. For example, the study

was able to show that a strict forest policy to reduce the production of wood products (i.e., the intervention) was only responsible for 36% of all displacements, the remaining 64% were caused by timber harvesting to meet the demand for wood products, which would have taken place even without the strict policy.

Empirical studies from Brazil

Finally, to focus on the EUDR, we review five studies with a regional focus on Brazil that have studied the effects of sectoral agreements, namely the Amazon Soy Moratorium, the Zero Deforestation Cattle Agreement, and the Palm Oil Round Table, as these can be considered as precursors of the EUDR.

Alix-Garcia & Gibbs (2017) quantify the avoided deforestation through the Zero Deforestation Cattle Agreement in Brazil by analysing the leakage of activities between different regions. To model deforestation, they use a stratified grid of sample points from the part of the states of Mato Grosso and Pará located in the Amazon biome. Using the Landsat-based deforestation measurement tool PRODES, the sample grid was analysed for deforestation in the years 2007-2014. The sample grid was then supplemented with the locations and catchment areas of the various slaughterhouses. These differ in terms of ownership, some being part of the Zero Deforestation Cattle Agreement, and some not. The sample points differed by the exposure of each point to the different slaughterhouses, as well as by time-invariant variables such as soil quality and distance to the city. The samples were then analysed using a linear probability model with fixed effects, and no effects of the Zero Deforestation Agreement on forest cover were found. It was observed that a 6% reduction in deforestation occurred in areas that were already registered before the agreement, but this was compromised by leakage in areas that were registered after the agreement.

Le Polain de Waroux et al. (2019) and Moffette et al. (2021) analysed the impact of the Zero Deforestation Cattle Agreement and the Amazon Soy Moratorium. Le Polain de Waroux et al. (2019) analysed the impact of the agreements on the production structure of soy and beef in South America. They considered possible land-use or activity leakage, and a possible market-leakage effect. To test the impact of the agreements, they develop an area model to describe soybean area and pasture expansion, and a trade model to describe the soybean and beef markets, using a variety of data sources such as the FAO, MODIS, the Global Roads Inventory Project, and official Brazilian sources to collect and integrate information on pasture, cropland, soybean area, soybean yields, producer prices, climate data, transportation costs, and trade flows into the models. The authors use multivariate panel regression to estimate the impact of the two agreements on agricultural expansion, soy trade, and beef trade.

Their modelling did not find a significant reduction in the rate of soy and pasture expansion due to stricter regulations. Looking at the results of their trade models, they indeed found a decrease in beef imports from more regulated areas. Yet, also interesting is the large increase in domestic beef consumption. The study attempts to examine the statistical relationship between production and import trends and changing public and private deforestation regulations, but also acknowledges that their results need to be looked at from different angles. For example, while they found that European importers source more soy from regions with stricter deforestation regulations, it remains unclear whether these regions

have developed these regulations simply to maintain trade relations, or for other reasons.

Moffette and Gibbs (2021) analyse displacement and leakage effects in the Brazilian Amazon with a focus on the two agreements mentioned. They use the difference-in-differences approach to estimate soya, cattle and deforestation spillovers from the Amazon biome to the *Cerrado* biome. Their analysis uses the distance of production from the border of the two biomes as the main determinant for their theoretical framework (Moffette and Gibbs, 2021). Their results suggest that the Amazon Soy Moratorium generated substantial spillovers into the *Cerrado* biome. They estimate a per-hectare increase of 31% in soy in the border region of the Amazon and *Cerrado*. For the Zero Deforestation Cattle Agreement, they found an increase of 24.6 % in the same border region. However, they did not find deforestation leakage for the Soy Moratorium, but an 12.7% additional deforestation for the Zero Deforestation Cattle Agreement.

Villoria et al. (2022) not only analysed pre-EUDR agreements, but also included an implemented EUDR into their modelling. They analysed activity leakage in the soy market in Brazil using an applied general equilibrium (AGE) model with explicit coverage of subnational land markets divided into agro-ecological zones (AEZs). They estimated how much of the deforestation avoided by Brazil's Amazon Soy Moratorium in the period 2011-2016 was shifted to neighbouring agroforestry areas in Bolivia, Argentina and Paraguay ("BAP"), i.e., to countries with carbon-rich forest ecosystems and ample room for further agricultural expansion, as well as to other oilseed producing regions. The authors compared five different scenarios. a) The Amazon Soy Moratorium, b) The Amazon Soy Moratorium and other voluntary commitments to avoid deforestation, c) Adoption of a supply-chain policy to avoid deforestation that is legally binding for all exports to the EU (i.e., EUDR scenario), d) Adoption of a supply-chain policy to avoid deforestation that is legally binding for all exports to China, and e) Adoption of a supply-chain policy to avoid deforestation that is legally binding for all exports to the EU and China. Half of the impact of the Amazon Soy Moratorium was estimated to be absorbed by increased deforestation in parts of the Amazon outside the Amazon Soy Moratorium (with a leakage rate of 53%), while cross-border deforestation into Bolivia, Paraguay and Argentina was negligible. Eliminating deforestation from the supply chains of all companies exporting Brazilian soy to the EU or China in 2011-2016 could potentially have reduced Brazilian deforestation by 9%.

Table 1: Overview of empirical spillover literature

Approach	Focus	Main finding	Author/Year
Equilibrium modelling	Carbon leakage from carbon accounting/biofuel policies	Estimates range from 7% to 40% displaced carbon emissions	Atmadja and Verchot (2012)
Review of tools	Carbon leakage from land use-related policies (REDD+)	Identified gap in global leakage quantification	Henders and Ostwald (2012)
Review of tools	International trade-related indirect land use effects	Equilibrium models useful but limited in specificity	Henders and Ostwald (2014)
CAPRI model	Impact of GHG reduction targets on agriculture	Leakage effect up to 91% due to trade balance shifts and industry displacement	Fellmann et al. (2018)
Global CGE application	Forest conservation policies and leakage	Leakage can compromise up to 95% of environmental gain in telecoupled systems	Gan and McCarl (2007)
USFPM and GFPM models	Carbon leakage from forest carbon sequestration	71-85% carbon leakage within the US	Nepal et al. (2013)
GTAP-BIO and OSIRIS models	Demand restrictions for deforested palm oil	Minimal effect on deforestation (-1.60%) and emissions (-1.91%) in Indonesia	Busch et al. (2022)
Meta-analysis	Carbon leakage in the forest sector	Average carbon leakage estimated at 40%	Pan et al. (2020)
Review	Spatially explicit environmental leakage effects	Conservation programs' leakage effects within regions and countries	Pfaff and Robalino (2017)
Review	Capacity to spatially allocate indirect land use changes	Combination of methods can assess spatial spillover effects of trade	Parra Paitan and Verburg (2019)
Global MRIO and land use emission model	Land-use emissions embodied in trade	27% of land-use emissions related to non-domestic agricultural products	Hong et al. (2022)
Material flow analysis	Leakage effects in the Vietnamese timber market	36% of displacements due to strict forest policy, 64% due to market demand	Meyfroidt and Lambin (2009)
Stratified grid and linear probability model	Zero Deforestation Cattle Agreement in Brazil	No significant effects on forest cover; 6% reduction in pre-registered areas	Alix-Garcia & Gibbs (2017)
Area and trade models	Impact of Zero Deforestation Cattle Agreement and Amazon Soy Moratorium	Analysed agricultural expansion, soy trade, and beef trade	Le Polain de Waroux et al. (2019)
Difference-of-differences	Displacement and leakage effects in the Brazilian Amazon	31% increase in soy per ha and 24.6% increase in cattle in border regions: 12.7% additional deforestation for cattle agreement	Moffette and Gibbs (2021)
General equilibrium model	Activity leakage in the soy market in Brazil	Half of the impact of the Amazon Soy Moratorium absorbed by neighbouring regions	Villoria et al. (2022)

In conclusion, equilibrium models as well as input-output analysis remain the main workhorses to estimate market-mediated indirect policy effects on a global level. Coupled with associated material flows, life-cycle assessment or spatially explicit land-use models further allows us to estimate land-use changes and other

environmental footprints. However, several knowledge gaps remain. We lack accurate quantification of global leakage effects specific to subnational regions, products, and sectors, as current modelling approaches impose a trade-off between coverage and specificity. Causal attribution of land-use changes to specific policies (or types of policies, such as voluntary agreements versus legally binding regulations), especially for trade and supply-chain policies requires further research. In addition, the long-term impacts of policies on leakage and spillover effects are not well understood, particularly how these effects evolve over time and in different contexts. Lastly, little is known about the mechanisms and determinant factors that influence the magnitude of spillovers. Addressing these gaps would enhance the development of strategies to mitigate dampening spillover effects, correspondingly improving the overall effectiveness of environmental supply-chain policies.

5 SUPPLY-CHAIN CONTEXT AND POTENTIAL SPILLOVERS DELIMITED

5.1 BRAZIL – SOY

Brazil is the world's largest soy producer and exporter, with a highly industrialized supply chain dominated by large agribusinesses and international traders like ADM, BUNGE, Cargill, and Dreyfus. Soybeans planting, managing and harvesting is done across Brazil, with significant expansion into the Central and Northern regions, especially Mato Grosso and small-scale soy business only in the south. Dealers can sometimes provide soybeans from areas prohibited by national policies, or from other countries that end up mixed in a batch of soybeans supposedly produced only in Brazil. In this first part of the supply chain, shifting to the illegal trade can be another strategy (e.g., with falsely certified soybeans) to avoid regulation. Additionally, smaller producers find it more challenging to implement traceability throughout the whole supply chain, which may have repercussions on the market dynamics (Reis et al., 2023).

After production, soybeans are either distributed domestically and regionally or exported, mainly to China (Figure 2). The EU, mainly Spain and the Netherlands, imports soybeans and oilcake primarily for animal feed, biofuel, and industrial uses. The EU's soy deforestation exposure decreased from 56,100 ha in 2018 to 29,800 in 2020³, reflecting an overall decline and a shift in EU sourcing patterns favouring regions with less recent deforestation and land conversion, while China's 2020 deforestation exposure was with 229,000 ha almost a magnitude higher (Reis and Moro, 2022). One possible leakage could thus be the accelerated shift in deforestation towards Brazilian regions that do not export to Europe. Considering the declining volume of exports to Europe compared to China, traders might decide to evade the EUDR by exporting to other markets.

³ <https://trase.earth/insights/eu27-countries-in-the-spotlight-for-deforestation-exposure>

Figure 2. Main countries where Brazil exported soybeans to in 2022.
 Source: resource.trade.earth

5.2 BRAZIL – TIMBER

Key sourcing regions from native vegetation primarily include the Amazon biome. Timber is also harvested in the *Cerrado* and Atlantic Forest biomes. For planted forests, key sourcing regions are in the Southern States of Brazil. Forest management and harvesting occur through forest concessions of public land, in private land, and in community-based and association-based land. Harvested timber is sold as roundwood (from plantation forests) or processed into products such as mouldings, plywood, furniture, joinery, and pulp. Processing predominantly occurs in Pará, with 70% of timber products sold domestically and the rest exported to regional markets and the EU (e.g., Belgium, Germany, France) and non-EU countries (e.g., USA, China – Figure 3 & 4). Downstream retailers and manufacturers sell, process and distribute the timber and timber products on the EU27 market. The Forest Code and the DOF+ (Document of Forest Origin) traceability system regulates timber documentation and transport, but informal and illegal activities persist in the market. Possible spillovers include land-use leakage, where restrictions on native forest roundwood might push illegal logging activities into unregulated or less monitored areas.

Figure 3. Main countries Brazil exported lumber and sawn wood to in 2022.
 Source: [resource-trade.com](https://www.resource-trade.com)

Figure 4. Main countries Brazil exported board and plywood to in 2022.
 Source: [resource-trade.com](https://www.resource-trade.com)

5.3 BRAZIL – WOOD PULP

Brazil ranks as the fourth-largest producer of cellulose globally and holds the top position in eucalyptus pulp production worldwide. The primary sources of timber for pulp production are pine and eucalyptus trees, comprising over 98% of the total volume (21.0 million tons of wood pulp in 2020) – mainly from Minas Gerais, Mato Grosso do Sul, São Paulo, Paraná, Santa Catarina, and Rio Grande do Sul. Additionally, pulp can be derived from alternative non-wood sources such as bamboo, babassu palm, sisal (agave), and agricultural residue like sugarcane bagasse. The supply chain, as described in D5.1, is dominated by contractors managing the plantation, harvesting, transporting and processing timber at wood chipping facilities and pulp mills. Some small contractors are involved in tree planting. Chipped wood is then directly exported or processed further in Brazil through mechanical or chemical pulping. Finished wood pulp-based products include paper, paper-based products (10.2 million tons produced in 2020), textiles, biomass fuel, and specialty products such as food additives and chemicals. Only 29% is exported, mainly to China and USA (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Main countries Brazil exported wood pulp, chips and waste products to in 2022. Source: resourcetrade.earth

Informality and illegality are also part of the wood-pulp supply chain, yet at a smaller scale due to its vertical supply chain in which a small number of multinational companies tightly control their entire supply chain. Additionally, the wood-pulp sector is characterized by a high level of private certification (e.g., FSC). Possible commodity leakage may occur if alternative wood sources for pulp are increasingly produced as substitutes and contribute to deforestation, if these are not covered by EUDR. Evasion could also be possible, with contractors focusing only on the Chinese or USA markets.

5.4 CAMEROON – TIMBER

Forestry in Cameroon is a major economic sector, contributing to employment and export revenue, approximately producing 2.6 million m³ in 2020. The main timber products exported to the EU are sawn wood, veneer, and logs.

Forest management takes place in forest concessions and council forests, located in Permanent Forest Domain (PFD), and in sales of standing volume - permits in unclassified state forests and community forests, located in Non-Permanent Forest Domain (NPDF). As described in D5.1, community forests' products mainly serve domestic and regional markets while others, mainly formal timber sources and processing routes, including some logs in raw form, feed all available markets. Traceability to the plot already exists as part of a national timber traceability system (SIGIF-2). Informal and illegal activities, such as unregulated sawmilling, have been prevalent, with informal production comprising a significant portion of the sector. Between 2014 and 2018, the EU was a key trade partner for Cameroonian timber, highlighting the sector's significance in global trade. As of 2022, EU remains the main export partner, but China and Vietnam are increasing their importance (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Main countries where Cameroon exported forestry products to in 2022

Land-use leakage might occur if stricter regulations are valid for concessions areas than e.g., for forest communities, increasing deforestation in those forests that are directed to regional markets. Evasion tactics could include mislabelling timber from informal sources as compliant or redirecting unregulated products to regions outside the EUDR's jurisdiction, allowing the continuation of unsustainable practices while technically adhering to the policy.

5.5 GABON - TIMBER

Gabon's forestry sector, with 88% of forestland covered by state-owned forest, is the second largest employer after public services, contributing 3–5% to the national GDP (African Natural Resources Centre, 2021). The sector has been growing, particularly with the implementation of the Forest Code in 2001 requiring logging companies to undertake sustainable management of their concessions, and in 2009 requiring that 100% of timber be processed in the country integrating wood processing prior to export (Hetemäki et al., 2023). Additionally, in 2022 it has been decided that FSC certification will become mandatory for all concessions, with a deadline currently set to 2025.

More than half of these forests are managed by private logging concession holders under the supervision of the Ministry of Water and Forests, 1.5% by community forests, while others are designated as protection forests or consist of young and mature secondary forests within agricultural landscapes (African Natural Resources Centre, 2021). As described in the D5.1, the first step in the supply chain consist in selectively harvesting trees with sustainable forestry practices (Bayol et al., 2012), and processing them (sawing, drying, and treatment) into timber products at sawmills in Gabon – around 4 million m³ of wood in 2020 (Hetemäki et al., 2023). These products are graded based on quality standards and primarily exported to China (lumber and sawn wood), the EU (mainly veneer and plywood), and India. In the EU, the timber undergoes customs clearance before being distributed to manufacturers who produce finished goods like furniture and construction materials, then sold in retail stores

and used for domestic consumption within EU countries. Throughout the process, waste materials are managed and recycled where possible (cf. D5.1).

Figure 7. Main countries Gabon exported forestry products to in 2022.
Source: resourcetrade.earth

Stringent regulations in these regions could lead to a shift in logging activities to areas with less rigorous environmental oversight, for instance, smaller companies that might have limited resources to comply with EUDR or are not covered by the mandatory FSC, thereby undermining the deforestation reduction. Logging concession holders might prioritize selling to markets with lower regulatory standards, reallocating particularly lumbers and sawn wood demanded by China, from high-risk sources and evading strict policies. With China being the largest importer (Figure 7), Gabonese producers could decide to export more lumber to China than Europe.

With the alignment between EUDR and the mandatory FSC, the tracking of non-deforested products is supported, possibly stabilizing the trade with Europe. Additionally, Europe's demand for Chinese finished wood products could act as incentive for Chinese companies to acquire certified wood.

BOX 2: OTHER TRADE-RELATED REGULATIONS IN TARGET COUNTRIES

As described in Sotirov et al. (2020, 2022), and further analysed and updated in D4.1, 4.2 and 4.3, numerous key policies and governance mechanisms at the global, supranational and national level have been introduced to regulate legal and/or sustainable forest and ecosystem-risk commodity supply chains. While aiming to reduce deforestation, these policies might also lead to unintended consequences such as increased pressure on smallholder farmers or supply chain disruptions in producer countries, exacerbating economic instability and potentially encouraging less transparent, informal markets. We here summarise the key legally binding transnational policies and linked to private law with relevance for the EU (as a major consumer and trader of FERCs) and Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon (as relevant FERC producers), all selected as case studies in the CLEVER research project and described in D4.2.

The **FLEGT** initiative, launched in 2003, promote legal timber trade through Voluntary Partnership Agreements (VPAs) between the EU and timber-producing countries. **The EU Timber Regulation** (EU Regulation No 995/2010, **EUTR**), applied in 2013, is a demand-side legally binding market-correcting regulation, complementing FLEGT. It enforces legality in timber sourcing, requiring operators to ensure that only legally harvested timber enters the EU market, thereby strengthening supply chains by eliminating illegal logging. However, the degree of success also relies on market demand for legal and sustainable timber, which, if insufficient or due to lack of consumer awareness, could attenuate VPA (Khanal et al., 2024). Cameroon's FLEGT-VPA, albeit legally binding, stands in competition with the EUDR, since the latter explicitly gives a limited and lowered recognition of the VPA standards. Thus, the EUDR threatens their legitimacy and competes in environmentally regulating the soy and timber sectors. This highlights incoherence regarding the EUDR standards with certain producer country governance mechanisms. Post-EUTR initiation, supply was estimated to have decreased, with higher import prices, and lower import quantities of tropical hardwood lumber (Rougieux and Jonsson, 2021), due to compliance costs excluding non-certified suppliers from the EU traders supply chain or reducing the export to the European market. The EUTR will be repealed by the EUDR with effect from 30 December 2024, which expands this approach by integrating production legality with sustainability standards, reinforcing the due diligence obligations for importers and traders and covering also forest-risk commodities (FRCs) like cocoa, coffee, and soy, beyond timber. Leakage or evasion mechanisms may continue or be amplified by the EUDR.

The **Amazon Soy Moratorium** (2006) and the **Zero Deforestation Cattle Agreement** (2009) are sectoral agreements in which the largest soy traders and meat processors have committed themselves not to buy soybeans or meat from areas that were deforested after the cut-off date. There is a risk of leakage to other regions or commodities, potentially shifting deforestation patterns without reducing it overall. Under the Soy Moratorium, on-property leakage may occur when soy farmers continue to deforest for non-soy land uses such as cattle ranching. Local leakage occurs under Brazil's cattle agreements when ranchers move their cattle from a ranch with deforestation to one free of clearing to 'launder' cattle, or when they sell to slaughterhouses that are not part of the agreement (Lambin et al., 2018). For the Amazon Soy Moratorium, since it is not legally binding (mandatory), like the Brazilian Forest Code, the incoherent standards of the EUDR (e.g., cut-off date) may delegitimize its standards and existence, since it is privately and voluntarily governed.

Certifications, in the forestry sector, the multistakeholder Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) and the industry-led Program Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC) and in the soy market, the Round Table on Responsible Soy (RTRS) may have limited influence, rewarding compliance with little additional impact, and unlikely to influence large regions (Lambin et al., 2018). Also here, a race to the bottom is possible where stakeholders certify their products in countries with lower standards, reducing the participation in certification schemes.

6 STAKEHOLDER INTERVIEWS: EXPECTED REACTIONS TO THE EUDR AND POTENTIAL POLICY IMPACTS

Within the CLEVER project, 200 interviews with stakeholders from the different case study countries/regions along these supply chains were conducted from October 2023 to April 2024. In the following, we summarize how stakeholders expressed themselves about potential policy impacts in these interviews. For a detailed description of the employed methods, see D5.1.

6.1 BRAZIL

Europe does not have the biggest share in Brazilian export markets, particularly compared to domestic meat or wood markets (e.g., I166; I189; I200), but it is still of quality and pays more for specific standards or species (e.g., timber) (e.g., I145; I155; I191). Most interviewees in both agriculture and forestry sectors shared their feeling of uncertainty as to whether the EU market will shrink; they understand this as a concern (e.g., I136; I180; I185). Some think that a further shift to Chinese markets will occur, unless they get paid more for their EU compliance (e.g., I174; I176; I190). It might be a discourse of those unhappy with the EUDR, or only a short-term solution until the market has adapted to the EUDR (I168; I171). An international organization representative and a public employee foresaw shifting trade flows: *"the ports in the South of Brazil will increase their sales to Europe. Meanwhile, the ports in the North and Northeast of Brazil, which are more affected by deforestation, will shift their exports to Asia. This will result in higher prices due to increased freight costs, which will drive inflation and lead to more emissions because the shipping routes will be longer"* (I167, governmental actor).

The strategies most mentioned by businesses were overall aligned with the rest of stakeholder's statements, highlighting the implementation of new due diligence requirements (e.g., I171; I180; I191) and supply base adaptation to reduce supply chain risks (e.g., I187; I189; I191). Several companies have already good traceability systems for all sectors but see as main challenges the polygon definition and tracing of products (e.g., I185; I157; I54). Supply base adaptation, the second most identified strategy, involves adjusting commodity production for EU to 'safe' production regions, with some uncertainty as to where this could happen due to climate change unpredictability (e.g., I168; I171; I185). There is also a trend towards reducing intermediaries and potentially excluding non-compliant smallholders, thus requiring supply chain rationalization and simplification, particularly for soy, causing potential inequalities (I167; I160; I193). Mainly timber and wood pulp companies stated that they only see the transaction costs of this efficiency strategy, since they have already gone through such process under the EUTR over the last 10 years (I195; I143; I161).

Certification remains mostly unclear as a strategy, because it depends on whether it will help proving compliance with the EUDR (e.g., I172; I185; I168). For wood pulp and timber, most companies are already certified, but not necessarily for native species (e.g., I180; I188; I195); and for soy most are not certified, but larger companies informed having gained more interest in certification before the EUDR (e.g., I58; I171; I190). Commodity substitution was not mentioned as a strategy, as these companies have already well-established supply chains (e.g., I157; I164; I168). Those affirmative said that this may happen more among EU

consumers (e.g., buying more products that are not regulated by the EUDR if these become cheaper), rather than with the producers (I166). One company from the forestry sector mentioned that they are first doing an internal gap analysis to understand what needs to be adapted (I154).

All respondents see segregation as a possible but difficult strategy, particularly for businesses. Many have already a system of mass balance⁴, and see segregation as a complex and costly process (e.g., I171; I190; I158). For timber, segregation is somewhat manageable due to existing systems like DOF+, though challenges persist with informal and illegal sources (I161; I162). The wood pulp sector faces significant difficulties due to the high degree of raw product mixing in manufacturing processes, making precise traceability to individual trees challenging (I169; I170). Soy segregation is expected, where the sourcing will be from certain regions, but involves complex logistics, higher costs, and the need for collaborative efforts among traders to ensure deforestation-free supply chains. This is due to the commodity's way of working, where silos and transportation spaces are shared by different companies to reduce cost (e.g., I168; I166; I158). In the meat industry, with diverging opinions on the simplicity of segregating these products, the animal transport guide (GTA) provides the information of origin but remains related to the property and not the polygon (e.g., I149; I174; I194).

Overall, higher costs are expected from segregation, information gathering, and new data systems (e.g., I171; I189; I194). Most here are normative statements, saying that costs should be shared among European consumers, large traders, and producers, others saying it will not be a fair cost distribution (e.g., I185; I187; I190). The soy market is expected to have less costs levied onto producers, thanks to subsidies and the large traders financing the entire production chain (I193; I168), while compliance for the wood-pulp sector should present higher costs due to the ultra-processed products (I195; I161; I169). It was mentioned that the government could support the traceability platforms to support the producers (e.g., I174; I164; I165). In general, the biggest concern is that compliance with the EUDR will come at a high cost, highly bureaucratic workload and operational shift, yet with very low environmental gains (e.g., I142; I182; I195).

6.2 CAMEROON

Asia is increasingly recognized as the primary timber market, with many stakeholders predicting a shift away from Europe due to the EUDR imposing stringent requirements and raising companies' costs (e.g., I21; I40). Some argue that this will accelerate exports to Asian countries, particularly for roundwood (I20). However, others think that the EU will remain a significant player, valued for its stability and higher prices (e.g., I38; I39; I9). While large companies are well-positioned to meet EU regulations, smaller firms might pivot to Asia or Africa due to compliance challenges (e.g., I7; I8; I14).

The European market, noted for its diverse consumption, mainly receives processed timber products like sawn timber, whereas raw logs are often sent to

⁴ When companies opt for “mass balance” sourcing, the certified and non-certified products are mixed somewhere in transit or production of the end product. The final products can be certified up to a quantity equivalent to the amount of certified ingredients purchased.

Asia. The market segmentation is also happening according to the certification status of the products, with certified timber going to the EU, and non-certified elsewhere. The EU also exerts indirect influence through global supply chains, impacting timber trade even if it's processed in countries like China and Vietnam before reaching Europe. NGOs, public actors and research organisation clearly belonged to the discourse of the increasing role of the Asian market (e.g., I1; I4; I11). Businesses, instead, had mixed views: some want to maintain the EU as a major customer and see the new regulation as an opportunity to strengthen their competitiveness (e.g., I38) and others preparing to shift of market due to the strict regulations (e.g., I33).

Due diligence (DD) is a key strategy for certified companies (e.g., I17; I24; I32), with some smaller firms also adopting DD to retain EU buyers. Nationally, the forest information management system SIGIF 2 supports this effort by tracing legality of timber. Certification is crucial for compliance, especially for large companies capable of meeting EUDR demands (e.g., I6; I12; I13). Several stakeholders consider ceasing or reducing supply to the EU shifting focus or sell assets if compliance becomes too challenging (e.g., I1; I4; I14). Others consider it unlikely due to potential similar requirements in Asia in the future (I16; I17). Region-shifting and supply-base adaptation are less feasible; commodity substitution is rare. Some SMEs may partner with larger firms or relocate to low-risk countries like Benin (I18).

Segregation can be conditional, depending on private commitments, ownership of multiple concessions, or specific market requirements. Segregation is possible by selling lower-standard wood to non-EU markets, but generally challenging since forest management and auditing apply to entire concessions (e.g., I6). Companies may adopt segregation strategies depending on costs and market demands, with some using certified concessions for the EU and non-certified ones for other markets. Economic reasoning drives this approach, as companies might choose less expensive options to maximize profits. As one interviewee noted, *"I think they will segregate because... some logging companies even do that. They have an FSC-certified concession for Europe and other concessions not certified for other markets"* (I22, knowledge provider). It depends on private commitments or ownership of multiple concessions.

Cost-sharing for EUDR compliance (e.g. costs related to monitoring, verification and reporting) is challenging to quantify, with extra costs likely borne by producers or EU buyers. Most stakeholders mentioned that EU consumers will bear the additional costs (e.g., I7; I8; I12). Companies already compliant with EUTR may see minimal increases. If producers absorb these costs, it could lead to job losses as companies may seek to cut expenses to cover compliance costs (I5). EU subsidies or incentives are recommended to support producers initially (I4; I11). There was no dominant opinion among public actors' responses.

6.3 GABON

For many Gabonese interviewees, the EU represents a relatively minor market compared to the booming Asian market, particularly due to the high demand for timber and the significant presence of Chinese loggers in Gabon (I64). Some predict a decline in the exports to EU due to the slow process of Gabonese

companies to comply and achieve certifications (e.g., I45; I47; I50). Only a minority of Gabonese companies have the supportive certifications to access the EU market. However, those that do, value the EU for offering competitive advantages to be enhanced with the new regulation (e.g., I44; I51). Additionally, the EU is significant for specific wood products, such as plywood and veneer of e.g., Sapeli, Okoumé, being specialised in veneer peeling (e.g., I41; I61; I54). For some, maintaining trade with Europe is a strategic move for risk diversification in light of market disruptions, like the COVID-19 pandemic (I55). While some think that shifting exports from the EU to China might not be feasible, others believe that EUDR may affect positively other countries too, such as China: *“Chinese companies who deal with the price in Gabon will process it in their companies in China, but to be able to export the finished products to the European market, they’ll have to justify the legal origin or regulated origin of the wood”* (I45, NGO).

With the EU's new regulations in effect, companies exporting to the EU are adopting Due Diligence (e.g., I41; I44; I51) and intensifying their certification efforts. Certification is another pivotal strategy, key to simplifying risk analysis and mitigation (I54) and confirming adherence to legality and sustainability standards (I58). Certified companies often separate their certified and uncertified supplies, directing uncertified timber to non-EU markets where certification is not mandatory: *“at source, we have FSC-certified performance levels, but not all end customers necessarily buy FSC, so we're not obliged to sell FSC”* (I41, international business). Companies dealing with non-certified suppliers are working on improving their certification status, even though it's not certain that *“we can have enough legally certified suppliers to have the volume of wood needed for the product”* (I54, local business). Chinese suppliers exporting Gabonese wood to Europe also need certification, with some opting for the less restrictive PEFC (I49), though achieving certification remains a challenge for new suppliers.

The decision to cease or reduce businesses' supply to the EU market largely depends on each company's business strategies and the perceived return on investment for compliance. Some companies believe the new regulations could stabilize or even enhance their EU market position by improving the image of tropical woods and supporting sector growth (I42; I44). Companies that avoid EU regulations might find themselves *“trapped”* in less regulated markets with potentially lower prices. For smaller companies, the costs and effort of compliance might not justify maintaining an EU presence, leading them to focus on local markets. Larger companies, needing to manage risk through diverse markets, may find it necessary to stay in the EU market (I65).

Opinions on cost distribution varied across all stakeholders' categories. Several respondents (e.g., I42; I49; I69) think that *“it's the end consumer who pays the heavy price”* (I47, knowledge provider), although producers initially bear the cost. State intervention through subsidies might be necessary to mitigate consumer impact (I47), but the distribution of costs along the supply chain remains uncertain and dependent on market conditions and price fluctuations (I69).

NGOs representatives believe costs will be borne by producers (I45). Certified companies anticipate minimal additional costs since they already practice sustainability (I41).

6.4 EUROPEAN UNION

The EUDR may lead to spillovers on products through offshore manufacturing and unregulated customs tariff numbers for finished goods not covered by the regulation. Market spillovers are possible as businesses seek new customers in China, the Middle East, and other regions (e.g., I5; I6; I7). This could turn the EU into a niche market, if compliance costs become too high, selling deforested products to countries without corresponding standards. However, many observers think it is still too early to talk about effects (I18), and others are confident that Brazil will make huge progress with traceability systems to comply with EUDR (I13). Some mention the EU is known for being an 'influential' standard setter market for others.

The EU actor's perspective on compliance suggests companies have divided views on the potential of shifting regions. NGOs, public actors and international organizations consider the region shifting strategy as more probable (I91; I92). Some businesses prefer sourcing from countries with large, state-owned forests for easier geolocation data collection, potentially leading to increased imports from low-risk areas like the US (e.g., I2; I9; I10). In the case of soy, for example, major buyers like Costco are investing in long-term contracts and infrastructure to secure deforestation-free soy, particularly from Southern Brazil. This strategic pivot involves prioritizing low-risk areas and potentially segregating supply chains to differentiate between EUDR-compliant and non-compliant products (I29). However, concerns exist about bifurcated markets, longer shipping routes, and the need for traceability in low-risk countries. For some, region shifting is under discussion but remains unclear, with potential challenges in replacing supply chains and the impact of future legislation still uncertain (e.g., I17).

Some stakeholders mentioned to prefer sticking with existing suppliers, but companies may cut out middlemen and reduce indirect suppliers to ensure compliance (e.g., I76; I79; I85). This could push out smallholders who struggle to meet standards, leading to a rationalization of supply chains. Others acknowledge the necessity of adapting supply chains, especially in response to legal risks and challenges with smaller suppliers (e.g., I3; I6; I7), even though in the context of timber a lot of work has already been done to comply with the EUTR. The outcome remains uncertain, with some questioning the need for drastic changes given the ease of geolocation tracking.

Most businesses interviewed foresee segregation in timber, wood pulp, and soy (e.g., I1; I9; I21). They anticipate sourcing roundwood instead of chipboard from outside the EU. For soy, the move towards segregated supply chains is more pronounced, with interviewees aware on the need to phase out mass balance and credit systems (I29; I31) and a foreseen cost 10-20% higher, like organic certification. China's largest food company Costco is building huge silos in the South of Brazil (e.g., offering long term contracts, buying the cheap and deforestation-free soy for Europe) (I9). This might influence logistical choices, such as redirecting soy exports from Brazil's North to the South and adjusting port

operations to cater to EU demand (with e.g., high percentage of RTRS certification in Brazil's north in Maranhão expected to shift to EU sourcing from Southern Brazil). Conversely, others do not expect segregation (I18; 36), citing established trade relationships for timber, technical challenges in shifting pulp mills, and plans to apply due diligence across entire soy supply chains rather than segregating.

7 DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

Let us return now to our main research question, namely: what could go wrong between, on the one hand, the primary goal of reaching deforestation-free EU supply chains for the targeted commodities and, on the other, the higher-order concern of reducing global deforestation and degradation? Based on our conceptual framework on types and drivers of spillovers (Section 3), our review of empirical evidence (Section 4), and multiple stakeholder interviews covering important supply chains (Section 5 + 6), we confirm our ex-ante suspicion that many factors can, and likely would curtail policy efficiency, due to leakage and evasion. Hence, we would also need to apply rigorous policy evaluations to monitor, assess and improve the effectiveness of supply-chain regulations.

7.1 SPILLOVER MODELS

Our review of spillover models presented in Section 4 highlighted the availability of tools and methodologies to quantify spillover effects in principle. While several area-based conservation approaches have been evaluated for spillovers, particularly leakage effects, specific applications to supply-chain initiatives such as the EUDR are less common.

Based on our conceptual framework of spillovers and their drivers, some stylized expectations as to the extent of spillovers can be formulated from the relevant contextual knowledge, cf. Figure 8. At the regional level, the abundance of factors of production that are not subject to the regulation and that can substitute for the regulated input can induce spillovers. The extent to which such alternative factors of production can be substituted depends on their costs and the elasticity of substitution, e.g., whether and at what cost other wooded lands are suitable for production. Nearby land that is well-connected to labour access and capital markets is more likely to be converted, especially if the land market functions competitively. Inelastic output demand raises the opportunity cost of land not producing the regulated commodity, thereby inducing spillovers, especially evasion.

This is even more the case when the regulation only affects the demand of a relatively small EU import share of the total market, such as for soy. Any regulation imposed by a purchasing actor with a small market share may reduce demand, but the corresponding price changes are smaller than when that market share is high. Hence, small importers' actions have a limited impact on the profitability of production on non-compliant land. At the production level, the main drivers of spillovers relate to the costs of compliance relative to its benefits. The adjustment

costs of achieving compliance are high, making evasion more likely, while well-established supply chains may be stickier, reducing the risk of policy evasion.

The spillover moderators may interact with each other in complex and nonlinear ways. For example, divisibility of production allows for product and market segregation and is therefore associated with policy evasion, in general. But on the one hand, the non-divisibility in combination with very high adjustment costs and a low demand share from the regulated market may also lead to full policy evasion, if operators decide to avoid the market altogether.

On the other hand, non-divisibility in combination with low adjustment costs may induce companies to apply the stricter regulatory requirement for the entire supply chain, and thus effectively result in a Brussels Effect, i.e. a corporate 'race to the top' triggered by the EUDR's pioneer regulatory action. Therefore, the stylized moderating effects should be seen as an analytical stepping stone, rather than a conclusive model to support policy action. The moderators are explicit contextual variables that vary in their relevance across scales and time. The divisibility of production and adjustment costs are probably shorter-term drivers; factor- and substitution elasticities are more relevant in the medium term.

Figure 5: Extent of spillovers and its moderators

Source: Adapted from Wunder (2008)

We identified several research gaps. First, ex-post evaluation of land-use change impacts caused by policy evasion rather than leakage deserves more attention. This is challenging because there may be no directly visible effect on land cover. Therefore, the scale of analysis must enable a spatially explicit connection between decision-makers and the landscape. Using spatiotemporal variation in trade-flows at trader-level, as described in Box 1, is one step in this direction.

However, given the complex interactions between different spillover moderators, further research across scales is needed to comprehensively assess the mechanisms and policy-relevant leverage points behind different spillover effects.

7.2 EUDR SPILLOVERS ACROSS REGIONS AND COMMODITIES

In the interviews, only relatively few spillover effects surfaced explicitly. A particular focus was on policy-evasion strategies. One common approach featured across the three countries was an at least incremental shift in targeted export markets, reducing the share directed to Europe. Yet, given that the EUDR has not yet been implemented, understandably many respondents remained cautious in their stated predictions – and in some cases perhaps also responding strategically about a perceived goodwill of most actors to try to reach EUDR compliance.

Supply-base adaptation seemed to be a prevalent strategy considered by companies in Brazil. This might be driven by the secondary role of certification in Brazil, particularly for soy, opposite to respondents in Gabon and Cameroon. In Gabon, the state is pushing for concessions to be certified, and several companies are already, reducing the need for changing the supply base. By contrast, Brazil's more diverse landscape of certified and non-certified companies may lead to greater need for supply chain adjustments, particularly among traders. This must also be related to the costs of implementing new trade which may be lower than the increase in production costs associated with compliance. Interviewees also mentioned how the EUDR spillovers are a continuation of the EUTR, with many adaptation processes already started 10 years ago.

Leakage effects were discussed only in relation to Brazil's forest and agricultural sectors, with a segmentation of the exports from northern areas selling to less regulated markets, and causing increased Amazon deforestation, while southern Brazil would be trading more with Europe. The fact that deforestation in Brazil is interconnected with domestic cattle consumption, might reduce the EUDR potential impact. An EUDR-associated soy price increase in the EU could affect downstream processor competitiveness, for example poultry production in the EU, thereby creating a comparative cost advantage of non-EU poultry producers.

Inequalities could also arise with policy evasion, according to the interviews. In Brazil, this was mentioned in relation to the reduction of actors involved in the supply chain, while in Gabon it was related to the low compliance capacity of small companies (high certification costs, high complexity of traceability) compared to larger ones. With the EUDR thus favouring large businesses, this might create imbalances in local economies, e.g., also encouraging smaller companies to operate in less regulated markets, or to sell to intermediaries at lower prices. Considering also the costs distribution, it is expected that prices of products in Europe will be larger to re-direct the compliance costs towards the buyers and final consumers.

Table 2 provides a summary overview of the main results about potential spillover effects of the EUDR implementation, as perceived by the interviewed stakeholders.

Table 2. Potential spillover effects discussed in the stakeholder interviews

Spillover effects	Potential spillover effects	Brazil (agriculture)	Brazil (forestry)	Cameroon (forestry)	Gabon (forestry)
Leakage	Activity displacement	Supply base adaptation discussed as key strategy	Supply base adaptation discussed as key strategy	-	-
	Market displacement with larger deforestation impact	Increase deforestation in the North; these products are not for EU export	-	-	-
Evasion	Export to other countries	Mixed views on shift from EU market	Mixed views on shift from EU market	Shift out of EU markets is expected	Shift out of EU market is possible
	Export other commodities	Not predicted	Not predicted	Not predicted	Not predicted
	Shift to domestic market	-	-	-	Possible strategy of smaller companies
	Market segregation of exports	Expected but complex	Expected but complex, espec. for wood pulp	Mixed views	Not expected
Others	Inequalities	Due to streamlining supply chains and actors' exclusions	Due to streamlining supply chains and actors' exclusions	-	Small companies excluded from the EU market

*Boosting is excluded from the table because it was discussed only in the European interviews; -- factor not mentioned.

7.3 REGULATORY COMPETITION AND DISCREPANCIES

The interaction between various environmental and trade policies reveals significant tensions and potential synergies. For instance, while initiatives like the FLEGT-VPA aim to promote legal timber trade and combat illegal logging in respect of producer countries' laws, their legitimacy and effectiveness may become challenged by newer regulations like the EUDR, shifting focus from legality to broader sustainability standards, not least set by the EU, and partly being incoherent with the national laws. This policy divergence can create conflicts, as seen in Cameroon's FLEGT-VPA, where the EUDR's limited recognition of VPA standards now undermines its legitimacy.

Similarly, pre-existing sectoral agreements like Brazil's Soy Moratorium and the Zero Deforestation Cattle Agreement face risks of leakage and weakened enforcement, to the extent their stricter cut-off dates and sustainability criteria give way to the EUDR's laxer ones. Oliveira et al. (2024) pointed out the danger of regulatory discrepancies in the case of Brazil: the national law allows 20% deforestation per property after 2008, while the EUDR cutoff date for illegal deforestation is the year 2020. They identify that 91,500 km² of forest legally deforested between 2008 and 2020 can be used for EU exports, rewarding speculative land clearing behaviour in the past and limiting the leverage of the EUDR to transform supply chains.

Further complicating the policy landscape are trade agreements such as the EU-MERCOSUR (still not operational), which aim to increase trade volumes by reducing barriers, in contrast to supply chain regulations like the EUDR that impose restrictions (Sotirov et al., 2022). The inherent contradiction between environmental vs. free trade policies, as Fuchs et al. (2024) suggest, calls for clearer alignment and communication of goals to avoid undermining efforts.

Environmental supply chain regulations like the EUDR may also come to influence other trade agreements like the EU-MERCOSUR free trade agreement with sustainability and trade chapters: the proposal certainly irritated MERCOSUR countries, making negotiation more complex. Yet, if the EUDR would effectively mitigate concerns of EU actors about environmental dumping via imports from Brazil, this could reduce Europeans concerns of opposed parties and contribute to reaching an agreement. A key to winning the support of now opposed parties is to build in safeguards that deforestation rates will go down despite more free trade in forest risk agricultural commodities, in line with the EUDR (Sotirov et al., 2022). This would be good for counteracting emergent deglobalization, but increased land demand may also put more pressure on forests – although this may then no longer directly stem from the EU's commodity demand.

Like the EUDR, similar legislation on forest-risk commodities is being considered in the United States (US) with the US FOREST Act⁵, the United Kingdom with the UK Environmental Bill⁶ (Villoria et al., 2022), or is already in force such as in Australia with the 2012 Illegal Logging Prohibition Act⁷, or Japan with the 2017 Clean Wood

⁵ <https://www.congress.gov/bill/118th-congress/senate-bill/3371/text>

⁶ <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2021/30/schedule/17>

⁷ <https://www.legislation.gov.au/C2012A00166/latest/text>

Act⁸. This possibly indicates a global trend towards regulating more the sourcing of forest-risk commodities, with the European Union playing a role in allegedly setting the groundwork for these efforts. Still, the US and UK laws contain lower-level standards as they allow for importing of FRC from legal deforestation in line with national laws (Berning et al., 2022).

8 PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED

This report has aimed to produce a better understanding of indirect effects of supply-chain regulations, taking the EUDR as a topical, politically highly relevant example. It contributes to understanding the mechanisms behind, and moderators of indirect effects, including dampening effects like leakage and policy evasion, but also potentially boosting effects. It presents modelling approaches and empirical evidence regarding the likelihood, size, and context specificity of these indirect effects. It assesses five biomass supply chains in more qualitative detail, summarizing stakeholder expectations regarding potential spillover effects under the EUDR. Finally, we discuss policy implications and future research avenues in the context of supply-chain governance.

As part of the work leading to this deliverable, a joint workshop between the BEDROCK and CLEVER projects was conducted in Frankfurt on Sep. 11, 2024.

The complementary Deliverable 5.1 produced an understanding of how value chain actors respond to policies and governance mechanisms. Deliverable 5.3 will synthesize the insights from Work Packages 4 and 5 and gauge the plausibility of effects from the EUDR on biodiversity.

⁸ <https://www.rinya.maff.go.jp/j/riyou/goho/english/english-index.html>

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